

ELPEG

May 2022

Agenda

- 10.00-10.05 Welcome
- 10.05-10.15 D1 – Air quality
- 10.15-10.25 D2 - Water
- 10.25-10.35 D3 - Soils
- 10.35-10.45 D4 - Biodiversity
- 10.45-10.55 D5 - Natural Capital
- 10.55-11.05 Further discussion about new programme/any remaining questions
- 11.05-11.15 Discussion over the format of the ELPEG bulletins.

<https://www.hutton.ac.uk/research/srp2016-21/elpeg-ecosystems-and-land-use-policy-engagement-group>

- 11.15-11.30 Round table of up and coming policy issues
- 11.30 Close

ELPEG/ELSEG

Established in 2016-2022 SRP

- Natural Assets Theme
- WP1.3 Biodiversity and ecosystems
- WP1.4 Integrated and sustainable management of natural assets
- Links to stakeholders and policy makers

ELPEG – Ecosystems and Land Use Policy Engagement

Policy attendees
Short meetings twice a year
May, November
Bulletin sent out in advance
Round table discussion of upcoming
policy issues
Update on science

ELSEG – Ecosystems and Land Use Stakeholder Engagement Group

Wider stakeholder group
Meet once a year (January)
In person, longer meetings with more
presentations, discussions, workshops

Continue ELPEG and ELSEG into new SRP – by popular demand

SRP 2022-2027 programme structure

Themes

- A: Plant and Animal Health
- B: Sustainable Food System and Supply
- C: Human Impacts on the Environment
- D: Natural Resources (Robin Pakeman)
- E: Rural Futures

Topics

- D1. Air Quality (Andrea Britton)
- D2. Water (inc flooding) (Mark Wilkinson)
- D3. Soils (Eric Paterson)
- D4. Biodiversity (Ruth Mitchell)
- D5. Natural Capital (Kerry Waylen)

RESAS SRP 2022-27 Topic D1

Air Quality

Topic lead: Andrea Britton

Context

- Air pollution continues to harm human health and the environment in Scotland:
 - 1 Major driver of biodiversity loss
 - 2 Contributes to climate change both directly and indirectly through impacts on ecosystems
 - 3 Impacts on soil and water quality through changes to nitrogen and carbon cycles
 - 4 Health impacts disproportionately affect the old, young, and less affluent
- Many pollutants increasingly well controlled by regulation of industrial sources
- Urban air pollution (particulates and NOx) from transport and domestic biomass burning remains an issue
- Ammonia emissions, mainly from agriculture, have not fallen in line with other pollutants

Policy

- Cleaner Air for Scotland strategy, recently reviewed and updated in CAFS2
- Vision for Scotland to have the best air quality in Europe
- Delivery plan for actions to improve air quality within 2021-2026
- Key research areas to support CAFS2 delivery:
 - 1 Urban air pollution
 - 2 Nitrogen emissions from agriculture
 - 3 Nitrogen impacts on the environment

Air Quality - Topic overview

3 main areas:

- **Assess risks, impacts and mitigation of urban air pollution**
Focus on domestic biomass burning and impacts of urban Low Emission Zones
- **Modelling, monitoring and mitigation of agricultural N emissions**
Focus on issues around livestock and manure management to reduce agricultural N emissions
- **Understanding impacts of air (N) pollution and climate change on natural ecosystems**
Development of evidence base on nitrogen-climate interactions, prediction of impacts/risks, potential for mitigation

Air quality: domestic biomass burning and fine particulate emissions (SRUC-D1-2)

- Project PI John Newbold (SRUC)
- Collaborative project with SRUC and UKCEH
- Objectives:
 - 1 Improve the emission inventory for domestic and commercial biomass burning in Scotland
 - 2 Quantify contribution of biomass burning to fine particulate (PM_{2.5}) emissions and concentrations across Scotland
 - 3 To understand impacts of PM 2.5 emissions from biomass burning on human health across Scotland
 - 4 Evaluate the effectiveness of Low Emission Zones (LEZ) for health outcomes

Air quality: livestock farming and ammonia (SRUC-D1-1)

- Project PI Gemma Miller (SRUC)
- Collaborative project with SRUC and UKCEH
- Objectives:
 - 1 Identify measures to mitigate ammonia emissions from livestock (ruminant) farming
 - 2 Develop tools to accelerate adoption of mitigation measures
 - 3 Understand the implications of ammonia mitigation for GHG emissions
 - 4 Develop tools to demonstrate impact of ammonia emissions
 - 5 Monitor and evaluate new technologies for measuring ammonia emissions from livestock farms

Nitrogen Impacts in Natural Ecosystems (JHI-D1-1)

- Project PI Andrea Britton (JHI)
- Objectives:
 - 1 Review interactive effects of N deposition and climate change on Scottish natural ecosystems and identify gaps in knowledge
 - 2 Explore combined impacts of climate and air quality policy scenarios on biodiversity and function of natural ecosystems
 - 3 Determine the most effective mitigation methods for N impacts on Scottish ecosystems
 - 4 Develop metrics to measure N impacts and recovery

Engagement plans

- Stakeholder groups for air quality topic are varied
- Air Quality policy: Farming ammonia emissions project (SRUC-D1-1) and Nitrogen impacts project (JHI-D1-1) report to the CAFS2 Agriculture and Environment Working Group
- Biodiversity policy: Nitrogen impacts project (JHI-D1-1) outputs reported via ELSEG/ELPEG
- Biomass burning and particulate emissions project (SRUC-D1-2) reporting via CxC targeted reports
- Engagement with scientific community via publications and conferences such as CAPER
- Broader outreach via SEFARI case studies, public events etc

Topic D2: Water

Topic lead: Mark Wilkinson (Hutton)

The James
Hutton
Institute

Moredun

SRUC

Edinburgh Napier
UNIVERSITY

Scottish Government
Riaghaltas na h-Alba
gov.scot

SEFARI

LEADING IDEAS
FOR BETTER LIVES

5 (large) Research Questions

1- Droughts	2- Floods	3- Governance	4- Water quality	5- Drinking Water
What are the risks and vulnerabilities within Scotland, and how do we build resilience?	How can we continue to reduce the risk and impact of flooding, build resilience and maximise the benefits from nature-based solutions?	How can we innovate, adapt and improve the governance and management of water?	What are the emerging and future risks and how can we mitigate these?	How do we continue to improve drinking water quality?

Emerging Water Futures (EWF)

Objectives:

- Develop methods and use climatic projections, to understand
 - 1 The vulnerabilities of Scotland's water resources to drought and
 - 2 Future risks to water quality from nutrients and ECs (pharmaceuticals, microplastics, antimicrobial resistance genes)
- Establish a baseline of Emerging contaminants across Scotland to inform future response
- Develop and apply trans-disciplinary approaches to evaluate options to monitor, mitigate and adapt to future threats to water scarcity and quality

JHI- D2-1, PI: Miriam Glendell (Hutton)

Achieving Multi-purpose Nature Based Solutions (AiM NBS)

Objectives:

- Develop a multi-scale empirical understanding of NBS
- Assess the water-related ecosystem services and suggest ways in which the benefits can be enhanced
- Assess the state of river corridors and their role in combating climate change, via ES impact indicator groups
- Understand how to achieve transformative change via NBS that deliver multiple benefits and works across multiple sectors and scales.

JHI- D2-2, PI: Mark Wilkinson (Hutton)

Two smaller projects

- **SRUC (Hannah Grist):** Vulnerability of remote coastal communities to water challenges: Perception, valuation and coping mechanisms (CCV)
- **Moredun (Frank Katzer):** Rapid & specific tests for the identification of protozoan parasites in Scottish drinking water (PP)

Projects: Covering multiple RQ and varying size

EWF					
NBS					
CCV					
PP					
	RQ1	RQ2	RQ3	RQ4	RQ5

Relevant issues and policies in Scotland	NBS	EWf	CCV	PP
Hydro Nation Strategy				
Scottish Climate Change Plan				
Climate Change Adaptation Programme				
Green Recovery (inc. Nature-Based approaches)				
Water Resources Management Plans				
National Water Scarcity Plans				
Flood Risk Management Strategies				
Scotland's Third Land Use Strategy				
Regional Land Use Partnerships				
River Basin Management Plan (RBMP)				
Future SRDP/agri-environment measures/funding				
EU Water Framework Directive (recast)				
Drinking Water Regulations				
Scottish One Health National AMR Action Plan				

Water Pressures: Droughts, Floods, Water Governance, Water Quality and Drinking water

Relevant issues and policy development in Scotland

Stakeholders and policies

Engaged with 45+ stakeholders whilst developing proposals and will continue to do so.
Organisations inc. – Scot Gov, SEPA, Nature Scot, Scottish Water, Cairngorms NP, Forest Scotland, P&K council, Scottish Flood Forum, Scottish Wildlife Trust, Chivas Brothers, DWQR, Spey Fisheries....

Soils D3

Topic Lead Eric Paterson

Soils: Topic D3

- **12 RQs aligned to 4 headings:**
 - Soil Ecosystem Services
 - Soil Protection
 - Soil Health
 - Soil Monitoring
- **Policy Drivers**
 - No single soils policy, but *“integral to many policy areas”*
- **Projects**
 - CentrePeat PI Rebekka Artz
 - HealthySoils PI Roy Neilson

- **WP1: Establish National Peatland Observatory**

Underpinning data to assess peatland ecosystem service delivery. Help design an optimal network of monitoring sites (link Soil Monitoring Framework, **C5**)

Collect long-term soils and GHG emission data, also research to evaluate water quality (**D2**), biodiversity (**D4**); and monetary/ non-monetary values of peatland (pre- and post-restoration) (**D5**)

- **WP2: Indicators of Peatland Condition**

Vulnerability to climate/ land use change (drought and fire risk) Develop Earth Observation-based methods for ecological condition and GHG emission proxies (including AI approaches, **C5**)

CentrePeat

WP3: Natural Capital Accounting

Building on C-storage-based accounting to include biodiversity, water regulation and cultural services provided by peatland. MAC curves (**D5**)

WP4: Particulate organic C losses from peatland

Addresses an important knowledge gap for peatland carbon budgets, linked with Erosion Risk Modelling (**C3**)

Research will include evaluation of drought and fire risks

WP5: Develop meta-model to inform UK GHG Inventories

Model annual carbon and water budgets for peatland monitoring sites (**C5**)

Assess management x climate drivers

Spatially resolved CO₂ and CH₄ emissions

CentrePeat: Engagement

Healthy Soils – for a green recovery

■ WP1: Soil Ecosystem Services

Explicit consideration of multifunctionality: trade-offs/ synergies

Current status of soils and vulnerability to change

Exploit existing platforms (inc. ACE, CSC, Glensaugh, SRUC Dairy)

Develop physical, chemical & biological indicators (inc. SOM stability)

Iterative model scenario testing/ validation (C2, C5)

■ WP2: Soil Protection and Management

System understanding across land use scenarios (C3)

Develop management interventions to protect soils

Plant genotype, novel rotations, nutrient management, cover crops...(B3)

Source: The Challenge of Feeding the World Sustainably: Summary of the US-UK Scientific Forum on Sustainable Agriculture, 2021

Healthy Soils – for a green recovery

WP3: Assessment of Scotland's Soil Health

Building on CxC Soil Health Project

Review thresholds for soil metrics

Resilience to land use and climate drivers (fire, biodiversity, GHG, water quality)

Use of existing (UPC) and novel data

Test/ validate remote and proximal sensing techniques

Digital Soil Assessment linking to the Soil Monitoring Framework (C5)

WP4: Informing the Importance of Scottish Soils

Create a hub for SRP Soils KE (establish a stakeholders' *Scottish Soils Network*)

Building on interactions from previous SRP and co-construction process

Figure 3: Schematic for cross theme engagement and delivery to policy, stakeholders and CKEI

Heathy Soils, D3 and SRP Stakeholder Engagement

- **Soils bulletin – produced every 4 months**
 - Year 1: scene setting; including input from stakeholders
 - Co-ordinated by Healthy Soils WP4 (Lead Ken Loades), acting as a hub for raising awareness of SRP Soils research
- **Events**
 - Annual soils workshop/seminar
 - ScotGrass (confirmed May 2022)
 - Arable Scotland (confirmed July 2022)
 - Royal Highland Show (confirmed June 2022)
 - Potatoes in Practice (tbc August 2022)
 - World Congress of Soil Science (confirmed August 2022)
 - Groundswell (tbc June 2022)
- **Other opportunities**
 - Scottish soils website
 - Podcasting – starting 2023
 - Soils Café and Soils Awareness talks

D4 Biodiversity

Topic Lead Ruth Mitchell

D4 Biodiversity

- 22 Research questions
- 7 projects
- SRUC
- RBGE
- Moredun
- JHI

JHI-D4-1: People and Nature. PI: Antonia Eastwood

Policy drivers: IPBES indirect drivers, Green recovery, The Dasgupta review

Planned Research Covering:

- Nature - people and nature - economy relationships
- Enabling inclusivity in biodiversity narratives
- Enabling transformative biodiversity research and change
- Harnessing Green/Blue Infrastructure for people and nature

JHI-D4-2: Identifying the causes of biodiversity change with specific references to the IPBES drivers

PI: Robin Pakeman

Policy drivers: IPBES report, Scottish Biodiversity Strategy

Planned Research Covering:

- Building resilience and sustainable use (global change impacts on sustainable upland land use, collective landscape management for farmland biodiversity)
- Apportioning biodiversity change to different drivers (IPBES direct drivers) land use change, climate change, pollution, invasive species and direct exploitation
- Effects of invasive non-native species, pest and pathogens on ecosystems

Policy drivers: SBIF review

Planned Research Covering:

- Solutions to fill gaps in our Scottish biodiversity inventory
- What is special/unique about Scottish biodiversity?
- New approaches for monitoring biodiversity
- Terrestrial species indicator trends and habitat relationships
- Develop an indicator-function matrix
- Farmer-led monitoring protocols for an Outcomes Based Approach

JHI-D4-4: Habitat management and restoration PI: Scott Newey

Policy drivers: Werritty report, Woodland planting targets, UN 2019 decade of restoration report

Planned Research Covering:

- How can public and private sector investors, at low risk, restore woodland habitats for the most multiple benefits to society in addition to increasing natural carbon capture and biodiversity, and what land is available for this?
- What is the impact of Muirburn on nature and how does this impact compare to wildfires and mechanical removal of vegetation?
- How do our ancient woodlands function and how successful is woodland restoration?

JHI-D4-5: Protected areas to tackle biodiversity loss now, and for the future.

PI: Ruth Mitchell

Policy drivers: High Ambition Coalition (HAC) for Nature and People: 30 % of world's land and ocean protected by 2030

Planned Research Covering:

- A Seascope approach for biodiversity protection
- Genetic diversity and PAs
- Providing climate refugia in PAs
- Resilience and measuring success

MRI-D4-2: Assessing the impact of changing migratory patterns and population size and diversity of greylag geese on livestock and public health.

PI: Eleanor Watson

Policy drivers: Independent assessment of UK climate risk

Planned Research Covering:

- Investigating transmission dynamics of *Cryptosporidium parvum* *Campylobacter*, and antimicrobial resistance genes between geese, calves, and the wider environment
- Development of molecular tools to genotype geese and assess of microbial risks associated with migratory and resident cohorts
- Review implications of findings for major stakeholder groups

SRUC-D4-1: Seeking multiple benefits from natural carbon stores in the uplands.

PI: Davy McCracken

Policy drivers: Net-zero by 2045

Planned Research Covering:

- Explore the relationship between carbon storage, biodiversity conservation and flood mitigation to detect synergies and trade-offs and identify land management practices that optimise the benefits derived.
- Generate evidence to inform land-use management practices in the Scottish uplands that contribute to tackling the twin challenges of biodiversity loss and the climate emergency.

KE and engagement with stakeholders and policy makers

ELPEG – 6 monthly meetings and bulletins

ELSEG – Once a year face to face meeting

SEFARI case studies

Other engagement

Conferences

Scientific papers

Public events

D5 Natural Capital

Topic lead: Kerry Waylen, kerry.waylen@hutton.ac.uk

Presenter: Robin Pakeman

Natural Capital *“that part of nature which directly or indirectly underpins value to people, including ecosystems, species, freshwater, soils, minerals, the air and oceans, as well as natural processes and functions”*.

Nat Cap Committee, 2019

D5 Overview

D5 ITGF

RQ1i
RQ1ii

Appraising Climate Change effects on NC

- Risk & opportunity framework & mapping
- Exploring across levels and land uses

JHI-D5-2, SRUC-D5-3

RQ2
RQ3

Improving valuation data & methods

- Agricultural soil valuation
- Participatory ecosystem valuation
- Stock-taking & gap-filling accounts

SRUC-D5-1, JHI-D5-1, SRUC-D5-2

RQ4
RQ5

Using NC concepts & data for change

- Understanding NC knowledge uses by public and private sector
- Working across levels from policy to projects and with new finance mechanisms

JHI-D5-3 (incl SRUC)

Output s

- Datasets & maps
- NC Assessment frameworks
- Valuation methods
- Identification of feasible changes to existing accounts i.e. NCAI, ONS
- Recommendations for policy, planning and appraisal processes
- Insights for involving private sector actors & new financing

D5 Overview

Key stakeholders

SG policy teams, inc. RLUPs, CC, Enviro & Forestry, Agr & Rural Economy

NatureScot, SEPA, SWT

Forestry agencies and companies

Emergency responders & those working to reduce fire risk

UK and International initiatives for business & biodiversity, and sustainability accounting & metrics (e.g. ONS)

Key SRP links

C3 (Land Use); D2 (Water - NbS); D3 (Soils); D4 (Biodiversity)

Eventual impacts

Better understanding of Scotland's natural assets, their resilience to and responses to climate-related risks over space and time

Improved accounting practices & metrics representing NC

Decision-making processes that support sustainability: esp. by policy sectors and private sector (investments)

JHI-D5-1 Bringing in participatory approaches to widen the scope of Natural Capital Valuation

Aim: to widen the scope of natural capital (& ecosystem services) valuation.

- What are the gaps in current NC valuation?
- Which of the dimensions of value would it be helpful to consider?
- How could these values be captured/measured/valued to support more robust and end-user friendly participatory planning, knowledge transfer and decision-making systems?

PI: Maria Nijnik, maria.nijnik@hutton.ac.uk

JHI-D5-2 Climate Change Impacts on Natural Capital

Aim: to assess climate change impacts on a broad range of Natural Capital assets spatially and temporally, consequences for Ecosystem Service supply and to enable Nature Based Solutions

- Uses concept that risks and opportunities are a function of an assets' Vulnerability and Exposure to a range of Threats
- Will develop a spatial 'Risk and Opportunities Assessment Framework' to which climate change projections will be applied
- Includes use of existing modelling capabilities (crop, land capability, soils, water etc.)
- Will produce risk and opportunity maps

PI: Mike Rivington, mike.rivington@hutton.ac.uk

JHI-D5-3 Galvanising change via NC (joint with SRUC)

Aim: What are the potential uses & influences of Natural Capital concepts, frameworks & data

- In national-level policy processes,
- In regional- and landscape-level planning?
- In the decision-making processes of private actors and investors, especially in NbS?
- In designing instruments for blended finance

PI: Kerry Waylen, kerry.waylen@hutton.ac.uk

SRUC-D5-1 Understanding the value of Scotland's agricultural soil natural capital (Years 1-3)

Aims:

- Identify the underpinning natural capital assets for key ecosystem services produced by agricultural soils.
- Identify the appropriate biophysical metrics and indicators to measure the extent and condition of agricultural soils.
- Determine and apply the appropriate valuation methods to agricultural soils.

PI: Alistair McVittie, alistair.mcvittie@sruc.ac.uk

SRUC-D5-2 Synthesis of natural capital and valuation outcomes (Years 4-5)

Aims:

- Collate and synthesise emerging knowledge on natural capital from the Strategic Research Programme and elsewhere
- Identify and apply appropriate valuation approaches for uses including natural capital accounting
- Provide analysis of future trends based on natural capital and land use modelling

PI: Alistair McVittie, alistair.mcvittie@sruc.ac.uk

SRUC-D5-3 Modelling the natural capital impacts of land use policy and opportunities (joint with C3)

Aims:

- To identify the spatial patterns of responses to land use policy scenarios and indicate the potential configurations of RLUPs
- Map the spatial distribution of the impacts of land use change scenarios on multiple ecosystem services and their benefits
- To provide analysis of land use scenarios to inform decision making and targeting of land use policy measures

PI: Alistair McVittie, alistair.mcvittie@sruc.ac.uk

THANK YOU

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